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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has been a catalyst for the rapid development of e-commerce and the transition of a significant part of retail to online. Companies have had to quickly re-engineer their business processes to adapt to the new digital reality and maintain their competitive edge in terms of sales volume, active customers and quality of services offered. This article discusses the current state of e-commerce in the Republic of Uzbekistan and compares its development before and after the pandemic. In addition, the barriers to the development of e-commerce are discussed and some solutions to tackle the barriers are suggested.

Keywords: e-commerce, online platform, pandemic, Covid-19, internet, ICT infrastructure.

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COVID-19 DAVRIDA O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA ELEKTRON TIJORATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

COVID-19 pandemiyasi elektron tijoratning jadal rivojlanishiga va chakana savdoning sezilarli qismining onlayn rejimga o'tishi uchun katalizator vazifasini o'tadi. Kompaniyalar yangi raqamli voqelikka moslashish va savdo hajmi, faol mijozlar va taqdim etilayotgan xizmatlar sifati bo'yicha raqobatdosh ustunligini saqlab qolish uchun o'z biznes jarayonlarini qayta ko'rib chiqishga majbur bo'ldi. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida elektron tijoratning hozirgi holati muhokama qilinadi va uning pandemiyadan oldingi va keyingi rivojlanishi taqqoslanadi. Bundan tashqari, elektron tijoratni rivojlantirish yo'lidagi mavjud to'siqlar va to'siqlarni bartaraf etish bo'yicha ba'zi yechimlar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: elektron tijorat, onlayn platforma, pandemiya, Covid-19, internet, AKT infratuzilmasi

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**ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ В
РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В ПЕРИОД COVID-19****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Пандемия COVID-19 стала катализатором стремительного развития электронной коммерции и перехода значительной части ритейла в онлайн. Компаниям пришлось быстро перестроить свои бизнес-процессы, чтобы адаптироваться к новой цифровой реальности и сохранить свои конкурентные преимущества с точки зрения объема продаж, активных клиентов и качества предлагаемых услуг. В данной статье рассматривается текущее состояние электронной коммерции в Республике Узбекистан и сравнивается ее развитие до и после пандемии. Кроме того, обсуждаются барьеры на пути развития электронной коммерции и предлагаются некоторые решения для преодоления барьеров.

Ключевые слова: электронная коммерция, онлайн-платформа, пандемия, Covid-19, интернет, ИКТ-инфраструктура.

Introduction

In the modern world, trade relations via the Internet, electronic commerce (e-commerce), is gradually becoming an attribute of everyday life. Goods and services are purchased remotely and delivered conveniently. E-commerce, in terms of speed and cost, has become a more effective trading tool than the traditional method, since all transactions can now be carried out online. The integration of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the world economy makes e-commerce simply indispensable for the stable development of the national economy. Therefore, the government seeks to pay great attention to the development of e-commerce.

Literature review

In the works of foreign researchers, the term "e-commerce" means the sale of both goods and services online [1]. The Declaration on Global Electronic Commerce, adopted at the WTO Ministerial Conference in May 1998, interprets the term "e-commerce" much broader, by adding the phases of production and distribution: "production, distribution, marketing, sale or supply of goods and services through electronic tools" [2]. At the same time, researchers such as Schneider G.P., Rayport J. F., & Jaworski, J. F., Jelassi T. & Enders, Papazoglou M. & Ribbers, Yeh C.-H. Lee G.-G. & Pai J.-C.,

Wirtz B. W. Daiser, P. & Binkowska and others equate the essence of e-commerce with trade, interpreting it as the promotion, sale and purchase of goods and services on the Internet [3, 4].

Uzbek economists, such as R.I. Isaev, M.M. Karimov, R. Kh. Khamdamov, Kh. P. Khasanov, T.M. Butkeeva, M.A. Makhkamova studied the basic theoretical principles, formation, and development of e-commerce. They developed a scientific base to improve e-commerce, and prepared the source code for their further implementation [5]. However, there is a significant research gap on this topic in Uzbekistan.

A critical analysis of literature sources allowed us to draw the following conclusions. In our opinion, three concepts should be substantively distinguished: e-business, e-commerce and e-trade. The most general, broadest concept is electronic business. It includes a set of business processes, telecommunications networks, information technology and electronic procedures necessary for the implementation of entrepreneurial activities. Electronic commerce is an integral part of electronic business, an instrument of interaction between the seller and the buyer, in which at least one of the key parameters of the transaction for the transfer of ownership of goods and services is carried out electronically. E-trade is an integral part of electronic commerce and is limited to activities for the implementation of sales contracts only.

If the development of information and communication technologies made significant impact on the growth of e-commerce, pandemic situation accelerated the growth rate of e-commerce. Recent new report called "Covid-19 and E-commerce: Global Review" by UNCTAD, consumers have avoided stores and shopped online, causing ecommerce sales to increase immensely, almost tripled. Therefore, the topic of electronic commerce, problems and perspectives of the development of e-commerce in the Republic of Uzbekistan is imported today.

Research Methodology

The methodological basis of the study is the application of methods of system analysis, induction, synthesis, economic-statistical and economic analysis.

Analysis and Results

According to the latest statistics from Canadian online e-commerce and retail software company Shopify, 14.1% of all global retail sales come from e-commerce as of the end of 2019. In 2020, 17.8% of sales came from online purchases. This number is expected to reach 21% at the end of 2022, which means a 17.9% increase in e-commerce market share in two years. Growth is expected to continue and reach 24.5% by 2025, representing an increase of 6.7 percentage points in just five years [6]. According to eMarketer, online retail sales will reach \$6.17 trillion by 2023, with e-commerce websites accounting for 22.3% of total retail sales.

The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is planning to integrate e-commerce to the national economy as today it is impossible to maintain good position in global economy without it. For these purposes, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the accelerated development of electronic commerce" dated May 14, 2018 [7] and a "road map" for the development of electronic commerce for 2018-2021 was developed. The document provides for the improvement of the regulatory framework, organizational and technical measures to create favorable conditions, increase in export potential, development of international cooperation and logistics infrastructure, formation and development of human resources, promotion and popularization of e-commerce among the population and business entities.

Also, given the dynamic development of e-commerce, in February 2018, the Uzbekistan E-Commerce Association was established. Its main goals are considered to be the development of projects and programs aimed at improving the climate, increasing the legal and economic literacy of business representatives and the public, helping entrepreneurs in the development and penetration of new products and services. To the end of 2020, about 60 e-commerce entities are registered in the association [8].

Development tendency in the volume of e-commerce sales can be seen, the figures for the e-commerce in national economy is analyzed. The volume of e-commerce sales grew in 2019 largely due to the expansion of the Internet and electronic trading platforms in the country. The volume of trade via the Internet in 2019 amounted to 275.3 billion sums (growth rate - 6.7 times), which is 0.11

percent of the total trade volume in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan (in 2018 - 0.02 percent). (Figure 1)

Figure 1. E-commerce in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019

Source: The State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics (<https://stat.uz/uz/>)

. Accessed date 30/05/2022

At the same time, there is a tendency for the development of electronic commerce among the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. So, according to statistical reports, if in 2018 e-commerce was carried out only in Andijan, Khorezm regions and Tashkent, then at the end of 2019, nine more regions were added to them. The share of e-commerce compared to other regions was the largest in the capital (77.09 %), Tashkent (10.89), Fergana (5.37), Samarkand (3.11) and Namangan (1.88) regions. As can be seen from Figure 1, the leadership in e-commerce falls on the capital, and in the regions, it is much less developed [3]. This is mainly due to bad internet connection and access to internet communication tools in regions.

The year 2020 proved to be a landmark year for e-commerce: the COVID-19 pandemic was a catalyst for the explosion of e-commerce and the move of much of retailing online. Companies had to quickly re-engineer their business processes to adapt to the new digital reality, where consumers avoided traditional physical retail outlets, and to maintain their competitive advantage in terms of sales volumes, number of active customers and quality of service offerings.

The upheaval of the industry has forced retailers, including those who had not previously planned to operate in an online format, to start rapidly implementing solutions aimed at the effective operation of remote sales channels. Online shopping, mobile applications, logistics models and delivery methods began to develop rapidly, with online order payment systems becoming increasingly popular. At the same time, the lockdown period and, in particular, the severe restrictions introduced from March 2020 have enabled Uzbek people to take a different view of online shopping, making it an everyday occurrence for many consumers rather than something exotic.

Figure 2. Monthly dynamics of the development of e-commerce in the Republic of Uzbekistan during 2019 and 2020

Source: Article “E-commerce in Uzbekistan and worldwide” (“The editorial office of the newspapers” Yangi O’zbekiston “and” Pravda Vostoka ” 16.12.2020) (<https://yuz.uz/>) Accessed date: 29/05/2022

While there was a generally stable dynamics of e-commerce with slight growth and decline throughout 2019, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a positive impact on e-commerce in 2020. So, the first quarter was at the level of last year's indicators, then since the second quarter a significant increase has been recorded. This is due to the introduction of restrictive measures on the territory of the Republic. Consumers are being forced to adjust to quarantines and social distancing measures.

According to the International Trade Administration the e-commerce industry is in the early stages of development in Uzbekistan [9]. In the beginning of the second quarter of 2021, the number of internet users is estimated at 22.6 million – 19.4 million mobile internet users and 3.2 million fixed broadband internet users - in a country with 34 million people. To facilitate e-commerce development, the government charges only a 2% tax on online revenue, compared to a 4% rate for traditional businesses. Uzbekistan’s laws permit online sales of drugs and medical devices and permits electronic checks and invoices as legal confirmation of payment for goods and services. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan signed a 2019 memorandum of understanding with Visa to develop infrastructure for digital payments, and many banks offer payment software and services to e-commerce websites to facilitate processing of online payments.

Moreover, Uzbek Government took several important steps to boost e-commerce growth in 2020 and 2021. For example, according to the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy, adopted in October 5, 2020, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan outlines the followings in its development agenda [10]:

- to increase the length of the fiber-optic communication network built throughout the country from the current 41,000 kilometers (25,476 miles) to 250,000 kilometers (155,343 miles) by 2030;
- to grow the high-speed internet coverage level from the current 67% to 100% by 2030;
- to expand broadband mobile network coverage from the current 78% to 100% by 2022;

The Uzbekistan Export Promotion Agency established cooperation with Chinese e-commerce firm Alibaba in October 2020, creating a “Made in Uzbekistan” section on the Alibaba.com platform, where products of selected domestic companies will be exhibited; the government plans to provide financial support for the registration of more than 300 local companies on the Alibaba.com platform.

Among the fast-developing platforms in the national e-commerce industry, the most popular online platform is Glotr.uz [9], which allows local companies to create websites to sell products and services. Individual-to-individual transactions are more popular on Olx.uz, Asaxiy.uz, Olcha.uz. Several banks offer entrepreneurs and companies payment tools to set up e-commerce services on their websites and applications, which enable their customers to pay for products and services online. The State postal service company is testing its newly created national online trading platform and plans to turn it into a massive e-marketplace by 2025. IT Park Uzbekistan, which was established in July 2019, includes 398 resident companies offering different types of digital services.

According to the German company Statista, revenue in the e-commerce market in Uzbekistan is projected to reach 1,644.0 million USD in the end of 2022 and expected to show an annual growth rate (CAGR 2022-2025) of 18.74%, resulting in a projected market volume of 2,752.0 million USD by 2025 [11]. However, positive projections on the development of e-commerce in the country may be disrupted or slow down due to some obstacles in the following directions [12][13]:

1. Dissatisfying ICT Infrastructure and services. ICT infrastructure is quite literally the backbone of e-commerce. But access to high-speed internet is expensive, especially for landlocked countries in Central Asia. According to the E-readiness in the Transition Economies of the UNECE (UNCTAD B2C E-commerce Statistics) Uzbekistan took place 93rd rank in 2019 and 107th rank in 2020. The government of Uzbekistan has been investing in its telecommunications infrastructure but ranks only 118th out of 138 countries in mobile internet, with 18.39 Mbps download and 9.47 Mbps upload speed. It ranks 90th out of 174 countries in fixed broadband internet with 44.36 Mbps download and 44.51 Mbps upload speed. A lack of reforms in the telecommunication and other sectors concerned, as well as barriers to entry, State-owned enterprises, inadequate regulation and the

need to improve access, affordability and security all hinder the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan.

2. Weak or not structured legal and regulatory framework. The main barriers to e-commerce adoption are consumer concerns related to online transactions, including cybersecurity, data protection, payment security, digital certificates and signatures, refunds, and dispute resolution. Like most transition countries in the UNECE region, Uzbekistan is developing a legal and regulatory framework for a secure e-commerce environment, but still lacks some aspects of this framework, especially consumer protection laws (related to e-commerce), legislation on cybercrime and personal data security legislation. In January 2021, amendments were made to the Law on Personal Data, obliging foreign companies to store personal data of Uzbekistani citizens in the territory of the country. The amendments went into effect in April 2021, and communications regulator UzKomNazorat restricted access and issued warnings to international social media firms not in compliance with the law. In addition, inexistence of single regulatory law document leads to the incompliance of e-commerce merchants to pay taxes. According to the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, after the adoption of the single regulatory framework to control, record, and monitor transactions made in e-commerce and support e-commerce participants, there will be an increase in tax collection by 196 billion sums.

3. Disruptions in trade and logistics. During the pandemic, additional administrative regulations accompanied by increased e-commerce volumes have made the task of customs and border agencies more difficult, resulting in delays and costs to providers of logistics services. Delays associated with specific controls or new protocols at borders appear to be significant.

4. Low financial inclusiveness and IT skills. Despite the increase in online presence, many Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) are facing challenges in penetrating the e-commerce market and harnessing the benefits of e-commerce. These challenges include lack of the required skill set and IT savviness, weak digital financial services and others [12].

Conclusion and recommendations.

Today, in the era of technology, where the digital tools become people's inseparable part and in the context of the coronavirus pandemic and post pandemic, e-commerce is perspective and one of the main drivers of digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Although it is promising to increase day by day with its own waves and its development may seem without disruptions, there are additional incentives to increase the turnover of online commerce. The main factor in the large-scale development of e-commerce is the active use of digital information, communication technologies, and the improvement of ICT infrastructure.

In the way of the development of e-commerce in the developing country, following measures are suggested to implement in order to solve the above-mentioned barriers:

- to improve ICT Infrastructure: addressing the internet problems by ensuring accessible, efficient and affordable internet, technology tools. A key aspect of addressing these problems is covering rural areas, where online access channels remain underdeveloped and may be out of reach of even cellular networks and are not wired for landline access.
- to develop appropriate legal and regulatory frameworks: addressing consumer concerns related to online transactions, including payment security, data protection, privacy, cybercrime, electronic payments, dispute resolution, and related to electronic transactions. items such as digital certificates and signatures, refunds, etc. It creates favorable and secure environment for e-commerce
- to increase digital financial inclusion and fill skill gaps: developing financial literacy and fulfilling technological gaps among population in all age group. It can be done by trainings, short educative videos on social platforms: Instagram, Facebook, or TV.
- to improve trade facilitation and logistics: implementing of the WTO Trade Facilitation Agreement, and where appropriate even pursuing advanced digital solutions that are not part of the Agreement. This would involve, first, identification and prioritization of smooth and paperless work in digital service provisions while at the same time working towards longer-term policy.

The government is successfully coping with its role of creating the necessary conditions for the development of the digital economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Further actions and strategies

ensure the consistent development of e-commerce, smooth adaptation of population to the e-commerce trends and to achieve results ambitious goals set for the near future.

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5 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

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